

A black silhouette of a cat walking across a utility pole. The pole is vertical, and the cat is walking along a horizontal cross-arm. Several power lines are visible, extending from the pole towards the top right of the frame.

Public Utility Data Liberation

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The Challenge

- The new energy system we are building is intrinsically more dynamic and complex.
- Energy economics, finance, technology, policy, politics, markets, and business models are all changing rapidly.
- The nature of our future carbon-free energy system is still uncertain.
- Policy design & evaluation, system planning, and operations are all becoming more data & modeling intensive.
- Access to data (and models) is not evenly distributed.
- This impacts the cost, reliability, and equity of the system we end up building.

Credit: PyPSA-USA

Walled (Data) Gardens

- Expensive!
 - Can't share or build on the data.
 - Processing is a Black Box.
 - Good for profitable, proprietary uses. Bad for public-interest uses.
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- Leads to information asymmetry.
 - Inequitable participation in policy making and regulation.
 - Status quo bias.

S&P Global
Market Intelligence

The Perils of DIY Data

- The data is public, but it's a mess.
- Data wrangling is seen as a chore, not rewarded.
- Results in a lack of specialized skills & infrastructure.
- DIY data is not (typically) reproducible or maintained.
- Lots of duplicated effort, not much accumulation of shared value.
- “Having access to analysis-ready data can mean a research project takes months instead of years.”

Public Utility Data Liberation

- Centralize & Share to accumulate value and reduce duplicated effort
- Specialize in data engineering
- Facilitate incremental contributions
- Continuous integration
- Regular versioned releases
- Transparent
- Reproducible
- Reusable (legal + technical)

What PUDL Does

- Monthly archives of input data
- Nightly builds & data validation
- Quarterly stable data releases
- Formalize structure of diverse, semi-structured inputs
- Ensure all outputs use the same data formats / access methods
- Link related datasets (semi-) programmatically
- Push to distribution channels
- **EIA:** 860, 860M, 861, 923, 930, AEO, bulk API data
- **FERC:** Forms 1 & 714 (+2, 6, & 60)
- **EPA:** Hourly Emissions
- **NREL:** Annual Technology Baseline
- **PHMSA:** Annual Natural Gas Reports
- Hourly wind & solar generation profiles

Tools of Our Trade

- Adopt software & data engineering industry best practices
- Version control, software testing, data validation, orchestration
- Python and SQL
- Strong, rich data types
- Tidy (normalized) tabular data
- Database and Parquet outputs

What's Next for PUDL?

- Open Source Ecosystem
 - Governance
 - Distributed Funding
- Early career researcher trainings
- Natural gas & weather data
- More data linkages
- More unstructured data
- Infrastructure scaling
- Support for open source modelers
- Support for Excel & CSV users

Workshops & Seminars

catalyst.coop/events

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Open Energy Data Office Hours

We're Hiring!

